

NOTES

Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with 2',4'-Dihydroxy-5'-(4-methoxy)cinnamoyl-4-methoxychalcone

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2'-Hydroxychalcone and its substituted derivatives are reported to form coordination complexes with various bivalent metal ions^{1,2}. There has been no report of bichalcone complexes and hence an attempt was made to isolate and characterise the bichalcone complexes with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

2',4'-Dihydroxy-5'-(4-methoxy)cinnamoyl-4-methoxychalcone³: 2,4-Dihydroxy-5-acetylacetophenone (1) was prepared by the reaction of acetic anhydride and resorcinol in presence of ZnCl₂. Compound 1 (1 g) was mixed with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (2 ml) in ethanol (20 ml) and aqueous KOH (10 g in 10 ml of water) was added. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 h. The yellow solid obtained on acidification with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid, was collected and recrystallised from acetone-ethanol (1 : 1) mixture. The product was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 184–86°.

Metal complexes: The ligand (10 mmol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was treated with 1 M NaOH (2 ml). The mixture was then added slowly with constant stirring to a solution of NiSO₄·6H₂O (5 mmol) in water (100 ml), and kept for 1 h and cooled in ice. The precipitated yellow complex was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over fused CaCl₂. A similar procedure

was followed for preparing Cu^{II} complex using CuSO₄·5H₂O. Analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Conductance measurements were carried out in 10⁻³ M DMF solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature were determined by Gouy's method. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region 4 000–200 cm⁻¹ using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Electronic spectral measurements were made on DMF solution of the complex in a Carl-Zeiss uv-vis spectrophotometer. Results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductances of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in DMF indicated their non-electrolytic nature. μ_{eff} value of 3.7 B.M. for the Ni^{II} complex corresponded to octahedral geometry. The Cu^{II} complex showed a magnetic moment of 1.9 B.M. which is in accordance with the spin-only value.

The bands at 13 480 and 22 300 cm⁻¹ for Ni^{II} complex could be assigned to ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) transitions in an octahedral field⁶. The ligand field parameters^{7,8} *Dq* and *B* were found to be 798 and 858 cm⁻¹, respectively. The magnitude of the parameter *B* was less than the free-ion value (1 040 cm⁻¹) for Ni^{II}. The 13 540 cm⁻¹ band and a shoulder at 21 720 cm⁻¹ for the Cu^{II} complex could be assigned to ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_g transitions indicating distorted octahedral geometry. The bands at 28 380 cm⁻¹ for the Ni^{II} complex and 28 180 cm⁻¹ of the Cu^{II} complex were probably due to charge transfer transitions.

The free ligand showed a weak broad band around 3 400–3 600 cm⁻¹. But the ir spectra of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibited intense broad band near 3 400 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of coordinated water molecules. On the other hand, the δ_{OH} band in the ligand at 1 395 cm⁻¹ was not observed in the complexes indicating the deprotonation of phenolic OH of the ligand. Further, $\nu_{\text{C-OH}}$ intense band at 1 200 cm⁻¹ observed in the ligand was shifted to lower frequency at 1 180 cm⁻¹ due to bonding to

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_{M} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	O	H		
NiL(H ₂ O) ₂	Yellow	12.9 (11.2)	60.01 (59.69)	4.48 (4.59)	3.7	6.79
CuL(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	11.92 (12.04)	59.01 (59.14)	4.45 (4.54)	1.9	4.85

the metal ion. The C=O band at 1650 cm^{-1} in the ligand got shifted to 1600 and 1595 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes due to coordination. The band at 1540 cm^{-1} in the ligand was assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ph-C=C}}$ and the frequency was lowered to 1520 and 1500 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, respectively. The $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ band was observed in the complexes around 600 cm^{-1} .

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Dibenzyl Sulphoxide Complexes of Oxovanadate(II)

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SULPHOXIDES constitute a class of ambidentate ligand capable of being coordinated to metal ions through either oxygen or sulphur atom¹. Thus, they may act either as hard bases coordinating via oxygen, or as soft bases coordinating via sulphur. A large number of sulphoxides complexes of metal ions are known¹⁻³. In the present note, we wish to report dibenzyl sulphoxide (BzSO) complexes of oxovanadium(II). Dimethyl sulphoxide and diphenyl sulphoxide complexes of oxovanadium(II) are already reported in the literature⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

Oxovanadium (VO^{II}) salts as starting materials were prepared by reported methods^{7,8}. The ligand

BzSO (Merck) was used without any further purification.

The preparation of the complexes involved the addition of an acetone or ethanol solution of a oxovanadium(II) salt to a solution of BzSO in the same solvent in required molar proportions. Some of the complexes crystallised immediately, while the others crystallised after concentration of the solution by passing dry air. The crystals were filtered off, washed several times with ethanol and finally with ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The physicochemical measurements were carried out as reported earlier⁹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) and the results of conductivity and molecular weight measurements reveal the molecular formula of the isolated metal complexes of BzSO as $\text{VOX}_2 \cdot 3\text{BzSO}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3$ or NCS) and $\text{VO}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 5\text{BzSO}$. Except perchlorato complex, all the complexes are non-electrolytes. The perchlorato complex dissociates in PhNO_2 and behaves as a 1 : 2 electrolyte. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes lie in the range 1.78–1.84 B.M. These values correspond to one unpaired electron per vanadium(IV)¹⁰.

Partial ir data of the complexes are given in Table 1. S=O stretching frequency in free BzSO appears as a strong band at 1032 cm^{-1} (Refs. 11, 12), while in the spectra of all of its complexes, it has been observed in the range $960-945\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The other important absorption in the spectra of BzSO is the C-S stretching mode which has been identified in free ligand at 682 cm^{-1} . This band undergoes a slight positive shift on complexation. A negative shift of the S=O stretching frequency and a positive shift of the C-S stretching frequency are indications of the decrease in the double bond character of the S=O bond and an electron shift from the aryl group to the sulphur atom of the ligand. The data thus suggest a coordination from the oxygen atom of the sulphoxides. In far-ir region, $\nu_{\text{V-O}}$ has been identified⁴⁻⁶ (Table 1). The occurrence of a single medium intensity band for oxovanadium(II) stretching at $990-980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of a monomer V=O entity in all the complexes¹³. The absence of a ν_3 band of ionic nitrate (D_{3h}) around 1360 cm^{-1} together with the presence of bands at 1500 and 1305 cm^{-1} , due to the split ν_3 mode in the lower symmetry, indicate the covalent nature of the nitrate group^{14,15}. The two combination bands ($\nu_1 + \nu_4$) appear as weak bands at ~ 1740 and 1725 cm^{-1} . Application of the Lever separation method¹⁶ (the separation being 15 cm^{-1} in this case) suggests the monodentate nature of the nitrate groups. In thiocyanato complex, the presence of bands at 2050 ($\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$), 840 ($\nu_{\text{C-S}}$) and 475 cm^{-1} (δ_{NCS}) is normally associated with the terminal N-bonding thio group¹⁷. This is quite possible since vanadium(IV) is a typical hard

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